

Blender software. Rigging & Animation of 3D Human Model

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About Blender software

- Blender is the free and open source 3D creation suite. It supports the entirety of the 3D pipeline—modeling, rigging, animation, simulation, rendering, compositing and motion tracking, even video editing and game creation. <https://www.blender.org/>
- Blender software. 2.79b Version. About, License & Development. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328677236_Blender_software_279b_Version_About_License_Development
- Modern accessible application of the system Blender in 3D design practice. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/312033613_Modern_accessible_application_of_the_system_Blender_in_3D_design_practice

Rigging » Introduction

- **Rigging is a general term used for adding controls to objects, typically for the purpose of animation.**
- Rigging often involves using one or more of the following features:
- **Armatures.** This allows mesh objects to have flexible joints and is often used for skeletal animation.
- **Constraints.** To control the kinds of motions that make sense and add functionality to the rig.
- **Object Modifiers.** Mesh deformation can be quite involved, there are multiple modifiers that help control this.
- **Shape Keys.** To support different target shapes (such as facial expressions) to be controlled.
- **Drivers.** So your rig can control many different values at once, as well as making some properties automatically update based on changes elsewhere. Rigging can be as advanced as your project requires, rigs are effectively defining own user interface for the animator to use, without having to be concerned the underlying mechanisms.

Examples:

- An armature is often used with a modifier to deform a mesh for character animation.
- A camera rig can be used instead of animating the camera object directly to simulate real-world camera rigs (with a boom arm, mounted on a rotating pedestal for example, effects such as camera jitter can be added too).
- **See also.** The content of this chapter is simply a reference to how rigging is accomplished in Blender. It should be paired with additional resources such as Nathan Vegdahl's excellent (and free!) introduction to the fundamental concepts of character rigging, Humane Rigging.
- <https://docs.blender.org/manual/en/latest/rigging/introduction.html>
- <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL3wFcRXImVPOQpi-wi7uriXBkykXVUntv>

Rigging » Armatures » Introduction

- **An Armature in Blender can be thought of as similar to the armature of a real skeleton, and just like a real skeleton an Armature can consist of many bones. These bones can be moved around and anything that they are attached to or associated with will move and deform in a similar way.**
- An “armature” is a type of object used for rigging. A rig is the controls and strings that move a marionette (puppet). Armature object borrows many ideas from real-world skeletons.
- Your First Armature. In order to see what we are talking about, let us try to add the default armature in Blender.
- (Note that armature editing details are explained in the armatures editing section).
- **The Armature Object**
As you can see, an armature is like any other object type in Blender:
It has an origin, a position, a rotation and a scale factor.
- It has an Object Data data-block, that can be edited in Edit Mode.
- It can be linked to other scenes, and the same armature data can be reused on multiple objects.
- All animation you do in Object Mode is only working on the whole object, not the armature’s bones (use the Pose Mode to do this).
- As armatures are designed to be posed, either for a static or animated scene, they have a specific state, called “rest position”. This is the armature’s default “shape”, the default position/rotation/scale of its bones, as set in Edit Mode.
- In Edit Mode, you will always see your armature in rest position, whereas in Object Mode and Pose Mode, you usually get the current “pose” of the armature (unless you enable the Rest Position button of the Armature panel).
- Full information on: <https://docs.blender.org/manual/en/latest/rigging/armatures/introduction.html>

Manuel Bastioni Laboratory in Blender software

The screenshot shows the website www.manuelbastioni.com/download.php. The header features the Manuel Bastioni logo (a blue cube) and the text "Manuel BASTIONI 3d humanoids" with the tagline "Open research for open source tools". A navigation menu includes Home, Software, Documentation, Download, Gallery, Tutorials, Planned features, Contact and Info, and FAQs. A central banner displays two 3D humanoid models. Below the navigation is an advertisement for "CRM и Call Center в едно" (CRM and Call Center in one). The main content area is titled "ManuelBastioniLAB version 1.6.1" and describes it as an add-on to turn Blender into a powerful 3D humanoids creator. It provides a download button with a license notice, release notes, and installation instructions. A SHA-256 hash is provided for verification. A "Download ManuelBastioniLAB" button is prominently displayed. The right sidebar contains an advertisement for "envato elements" and a list of "FREE ITEMS", "ADD-ONS", and "TEMPLATES".

Manuel Bastioni Lab (Characters). Download:
• <http://www.manuelbastioni.com/download.php>

Manuel Bastioni Laboratory License of the Code

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Manuel Bastioni Laboratory License of the Database

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All data files released in the ManuelbastioniLAB package, including all the meshes and data contained in .blend files or in any other 3d file format (for example .obj and .mtl), all the images and all the json files are released under GNU Affero General Public License 3.

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<https://www.gnu.org/licenses/agpl.html>

Manuel Bastioni Laboratory License of Models generated by the software

LICENSE OF MODELS GENERATED BY THE SOFTWARE

The AGPL can be an obstacle in case someone wants to create a closed source game or closed source 3D models using 3D characters made with the lab because the AGPL will propagate from the base models and from the database to the output models.

For this reason it was decided to consent a double license ONLY for the models generated by the official software*, NOT for the source code, NOT for the json database and NOT for blend files included in the distribution:

The default license for models generated by the software is AGPL 3: <https://www.gnu.org/licenses/agpl.html>. As derived product of the AGPL'd database, the models must be distributed under AGPL 3, with the same copyright of the database.

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Manuel Bastioni Laboratory Note about 2D Rendering

NOTE ABOUT 2D RENDERING

Rendered two-dimensional images or two-dimensional videos of a scene that includes 3D models generated with Manuel Bastioni Lab are not considered a derived product of the licensed 3D database and 3D base models.

Due to many factors (i.e. the transformation from 3D space to 2D space, the position and the type of camera used, the other 3D elements included in the scene, the position and type of lights, the post production, the composition of multiple characters, the path of the camera, ecc.) the original 3D data is fundamentally modified and transformed sufficiently that it constitutes an original work.

For this reason, the author of the 2D rendering is the sole copyright owner of 2D image/video created by him and the sole responsible for the use of his 2D image/video.

Manuel Bastioni Lab / ManuelbastioniLAB - Add-on

User Preferences > ManuelbastioniLAB - add-on

Blender software – Add Human Character / Parameters

Manuel Bastioni Lab (Characters). Download:
<http://www.manuelbastioni.com/download.php>

Armature / Appear / X-Ray

The 3D Human model. Edit Mode. Object Data > Display / Octahedral (Marked): Shapes, Colors and X-Ray

Pose Mode

Pose Mode

Rigging & Animation

Front Ortho View. Pose Mode. Selected Bone & Frame - 1

Animation / LocRot

Insert Keyframe Menu ("I" Key) and LockRot / Frame - 1

Selecting & Rigging

Pose Mode. Selected Bone & Frame 65

Rotation

Rotation ("R" Key)

Animation / LocRot

Insert Keyframe Menu ("I" Key) and LockRot / Frame - 65

Selecting & Rigging

Front Ortho View. Pose Mode. Selected Bone & Frame - 40

Animation / LocRot

Instert Keyframe Menu ("I" Key) and LockRot / Frame - 40

Selecting & Rigging

Front Ortho View. Pose Mode. Selected Bone & Frame - 70

Rotation

Rotation ("R" Key)

Animation / LocRot

Insert Keyframe Menu ("I" Key) and LockRot / Key - 70

Selecting & Rigging

Front Ortho View. Pose Mode. Selected Bone & Frame - 50

Animation / LocRot

Insert Keyframe Menu ("I" Key) and LockRot / Key - 50

Selecting & Rigging

Left Ortho View. Pose Mode. Selected Bone & Frame - 70

Rotation

Rotation ("R" Key)

Animation / LocRot

Insert Keyframe Menu ("I" Key) and LockRot / Key - 70

Animation Result

References

- **Blender Software**
<https://www.blender.org/>
- **Tihomir Dovramadjiev PhD. Modern accessible application of the system Blender in 3D design practice.**
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/312033613_Modern_accessible_application_of_the_system_Blender_in_3D_design_practice
- Blender software. 2.79b Version. About, License & Development. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36167.75687
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328677236_Blender_software_279b_Version_About_License_Development
- **Blender User Manual. Release 2.78. Blender Community. Mar 08, 2017**
- **Tihomir Dovramadjiev PhD. BLENDER CYCLES-CREATING HUMAN CHARACTER + HOLOGRAM MATERIAL-TUTORIAL.**
DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11225.01121/1
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324922895_BLENDER_CYCLES-CREATING_HUMAN_CHARACTER_HOLOGRAM_MATERIAL-TUTORIAL
- **Blender Rigging » Introduction**
<https://docs.blender.org/manual/en/latest/rigging/index.html?highlight=rig>
<https://docs.blender.org/manual/en/latest/rigging/introduction.html>
<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL3wFcRXImVPOQpi-wi7uriXBkykXVUntv>
- **Rigging » Armatures » Introduction**
<https://docs.blender.org/manual/en/latest/rigging/armatures/introduction.html>
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